

Impact of Nuclear Data Uncertainties on Reactivity Calculations of Lead-cooled Fast Reactors.

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ABSTRACT

The validation of numerical simulation tools for innovative reactor designs is facing new challenges, as the field of application of these tools is extended. For lead-cooled fast reactors, the core contains new materials which leads to different neutron behavior. It is therefore necessary to study in detail all sources of error that may arise during the resolution process. This article examines the uncertainties arising from the lack of knowledge about nuclear data in reactivity calculations for lead-cooled fast reactors. We show that the share of variance attributable to lead is small compared to the one attributable to the elements of the fuel for ALFRED, the studied core. We then perform an analysis of the benchmark performed by the ICSBEP Working Group under the aegis of the OECD Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA) with a view to assimilating data on the experiments that comprise it to reduce uncertainty. Assimilation is first carried out on individual experiments and then on groups of experiments. Several approaches have been tested for selecting the groups on which to perform data assimilation. We first tried to select the experiments that gave the lowest uncertainty for sets of experiments composed of up to five experiments, then we selected the experiments that maximize the coverage of the isotopes of the core. The results are promising, as we have been able to reduce the uncertainty arising from nuclear data from 1227pcm to 232pcm.

Keywords: Uncertainty Analysis, Sensitivity Analysis, Nuclear Data Asssimilation, Representativeness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Demonstrating the safety of a nuclear reactor core is a major step towards its commissioning. It ensures that the reactor under study can be operated within the planned operating ranges while guaranteeing the safety of people and the environment. In the more specific context of neutronics, this involves ensuring proper control of the core's reactivity and power in normal and accidental configurations.

To do so, scientific calculation tools were developed, which enable to simulate the behavior of the core and to determine the quantities of interest, such as neutron flux distribution and reaction rates.

The performances of these scientific calculation tools in terms of accuracy and reliability is well known for reactors in operation. The approximations made throughout the resolution have been studied in detail and the abundant feedback from experiments allows a good understanding of the discrepancies that may appear between the true value and the calculated one.

For innovative reactors and especially fast spectrum reactors, however, it is not the case. These reactors use new materials, such as coolant or fuel, which may lead to different neutron behavior. The performance of the calculation tools on these new reactors must therefore be investigated. It is a real challenge considering the lack of experimental feedback on the new designs.

The discrepancies that appear in the calculation of a quantity of interest (QI) of a core can be broken down into three terms [1]:

$$QI_{true} - QI_{calculated} = u_{ND} + u_{Mod} + u_{OMD}, \quad (1)$$

where:

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- $Q_{I_{true}} - Q_{I_{calculated}}$ is the discrepancy between the true value and its estimation by the calculation tool,
- u_{ND} is the uncertainty attributable to errors in the nuclear data,
- u_{Mod} is the one attributable to the approximations made to simplify the model, and
- u_{OMD} is the one attributable to the lack of knowledge about the core's composition and operation (operating and manufacturing data).

This article presents a study of the discrepancies attributable to the approximations made in the nuclear data evaluation on the reactivity calculation. Nuclear data are typically the reactions cross sections of the different isotopes present in the core and the fission characteristics of the fissile atoms. The study is conducted on a Lead-cooled Fast Reactor (LFR), a type of reactor that meets the typical challenges associated with the innovative designs: an extended field of application for numerical simulation tools and few representative experiments available to validate them. Since most experiments within the historical legacy are not lead-based, they cannot be easily incorporated into the validation process. Still, we believe that they can contain relevant information when they are used in a Bayesian calibration framework like it was done for the design of new experimental programs [2, 3, 4].

We will therefore compare the reactor core's reactivity sensitivity to nuclear data to the ones of a benchmark of historical experiments. Since the benchmark contains very few experiments with lead, we will first try to understand and quantify the impact of the presence of lead in the core on the u_{ND} . After demonstrating that the presence of lead has negligible impact compared to the composition of the fuel, we will attempt to develop a reliable methodology for analyzing existing experiments. To determine the relevant information they contain, we will study several representativeness indicators between experiments and the studied core. This study will give us a better understanding of the u_{ND} and will allow us to reduce it.

2. FRAMEWORK OF THE ANALYSIS

In this article we studied the ALFRED reactor core design [5] as our reference Lead-cooled Fast Reactor. We analyzed the experiments of the benchmark performed by the ICSBEP Working Group under the aegis of the OECD Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA) [6] to find similar configurations that will help reduce the uncertainty of the reactivity calculation.

2.1. The ALFRED reactor core design

ALFRED is a European LFR design of 300 MWth and 125 MWe, operating between 400°C and 500°C. Its core is composed of 134 hexagonal MOX fuel assemblies surrounded by 102 hexagonal shield and reflector assemblies. To simplify the calculation, the control rods were extracted from the core and some axial reflectors had to be removed to reach criticality. The core was modeled using APOLLO3[®] [7], the deterministic code developed by the CEA and the JEFF 3.1.1 nuclear data library. Each assembly is first homogenized at the lattice calculation step using the TDT-MOC solver (Methods Of Characteristics solver). The ALFRED core is then simulated using the MINARET solver, based on the S_N angular discretization.

2.2. The ICSBEP database

The International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) is a benchmark that contains a huge amount of experimental data, coming from all the available critical experiments and Zero Power Reactors (ZPR). A great work of data formatting was done, that allowed us to analyze the sensitivity profiles to nuclear data of the 581 experiments configurations with fast neutron spectrum and compare them to the ALFRED design's core.

Several of these experiments were carried out on the same experimental devices and they may therefore

show correlations that could lead to overfitting in the data assimilation step. To get over this concern, we kept only the experiment of each series of experiments that was the most representative of the core under study. Finally, the benchmark of study we selected is composed of 168 experiments.

3. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

3.1. Uncertainty calculations

The goal of this study is to reduce the uncertainty in the calculation of a quantity of interest (QI) attributable to a lack of knowledge on nuclear data values. This uncertainty is calculated as follows [8]:

$$u_{ND} = \sqrt{S^t Cov_{ND} S}. \quad (2)$$

Where S is the sensitivity profile of the core to the nuclear data, which means that it contains the sensitivity coefficient of the quantity of interest QI to the cross section $\sigma^{i,r,g}$ of every isotope i , reaction r and neutron energy group g : $S_{i,r,g} = \frac{\partial QI}{\partial \sigma^{i,r,g}}$. Cov_{ND} is the nuclear data covariance matrix which contains the uncertainties of every nuclear data value and their correlations.

For the ALFRED case, sensitivity profiles were calculated using the perturbation engine of APOLLO3[®] based on the Generalized Perturbation Theory (GPT) that allows the calculation of the bilinear products. The other sensitivity profiles were taken in the ICSBEP database and condensed to 33 groups.

We used COMAC, the ECCO-33 groups covariance matrix of CEA Cadarache [9] based on the JEFF-3.1.1 nuclear data library, that contains information about fission, ν , χ , capture, n_{xn} , elastic and inelastic uncertainties of most of the isotopes that can be bound in a reactor core. This matrix did not contain any information on the neutron reactions on lead isotopes, so we had to find this information elsewhere. We decided to add the JENDL 5.0 variance and covariance matrix lead part [10] to COMAC.

Once the uncertainty coming from nuclear data is determined, we want to quantify the contribution of lead to this uncertainty. As the uncertainty calculation is non linear, we compared the variances of the different isotopes to estimate their contribution to the overall uncertainty: $u_I^2 = S^t Cov_{ND} S_I$, where S^I is the sensitivity profile of the quantity of interest QI of the core to an isotope I present in the core, with $S^{i,r,g} = 0$ if $i \neq I$. The share of the lead variance is therefore the sum of the variance of every lead isotopes on the sum of the variance of every isotopes of the core:

$$s_{Pb} = \frac{\sum_{i \in Pb} u_i^2}{\sum_{i \in core} u_i^2}. \quad (3)$$

3.2. Uncertainty reduction with data assimilation

The experiments of the ICSBEP database give information on nuclear data that can be used to reduce uncertainty by performing Bayesian inference. By modifying the cross section of a neutron reaction on an isotope in the range of its evaluated uncertainty, it is possible to reduce the discrepancies between the value measured on the experiments and the one calculated with the nuclear data [11]. This process is called data assimilation and it allows to tune the parameters to get a more accurate calculation and reduce the uncertainty on the calculated value.

The uncertainty after data assimilation on a set of n experiments, labeled $(E_i)_{1 \leq i \leq n}$, called a *posteriori* uncertainty, can be written as follows [12]:

$$u_{ND}^* = u_{ND} \sqrt{1 - R^t \Omega R}, \quad (4)$$

where:

$$R = (r_{E_i/A})_{1 \leq i \leq n}, \quad (5)$$

$$\Omega = \left(\left(\frac{\delta_{ij}^2}{u_{ND}(E_i)u_{ND}(E_j)} + r_{E_i/E_j} \right)_{1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq n} \right)^{-1}. \quad (6)$$

With:

$$r_{E_i/A} = \frac{S^t(E_i)Cov_{ND}S(A)}{u_{ND}(E_i)u_{ND}(A)}, \quad (7)$$

where $S(E_i)$ is the sensitivity profile of the experiment E_i , $S(A)$ the sensitivity profile of the ALFRED core and Cov_{ND} the nuclear data covariance matrix. δ_{ii} represents the experimental uncertainty of the experiment E_i (that can be found in the ICSBEP Handbook) and when $i \neq j$, δ_{ij} is a penalty that represents the experimental correlation between E_i and E_j . As we conserved only the most representative configuration of every series of experiments, meaning that the experiments do not have correlations in their manufacturing data approximations, this correlation may come only from similar measurement techniques. It was not possible to study it on a case-by-case basis, so we set $\delta_{ij} = 0.3 \min(\delta_{ii}, \delta_{jj})$, considering that 30% of the experimental uncertainty could come from measurement techniques [13].

In formula (4), Ω is the neutronic weight matrix, describing the quality of the experiments. We see that for only one experiment, the neutronic weight is equal to $\Omega = \frac{u_{ND}^2}{u_{ND}^2 + \delta^2}$. R is the representativeness coefficient profile between a set of n experiments $(E_i)_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ and the core A . Each component i of this vector quantifies the similarity between E_i and A in terms of sensitivity to nuclear data. If $r_{E_i/A} = 1$, the dependence of A and E_i to nuclear data is exactly the same, and cross sections modifications that decrease the uncertainty for the experiment will decrease the uncertainty for the studied core. If $r_{E_i/A} = 0$, no information can be extracted from the experiment to reduce the uncertainty of the core.

Representativeness is a good estimator of the similarity between an experiment and the studied core, but it does not give any information on the isotopes that make up the experiment. If the calculated quantity of interest has a significant sensitivity level to an isotope present in an experiment and the core, representativeness will be high, even if a lot of isotopes are not studied in the experiment. To look more closely to the isotopes of the experiments, we used the coverage factor: $C_E = \sum_{i,r \in iso,rea} c_E^{i,r}$ that

expresses the number of isotopes to which the quantity of interest of an experiment E have a sensitivity of the same order of magnitude as the one of a studied core A , for each isotope and reaction that may

occur in the studied core [14]: $c_E^{i,r} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |S_E^{i,r}| \geq \frac{|S_A^{i,r}|}{2} \text{ and } S_E^{i,r} \cdot S_A^{i,r} \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$.

4. PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

In this analysis, we focused on the multiplication factor calculation. First identifying the uncertainty and the share of the nuclear data variance coming from the lead coolant. We then explore the ICSBEP experiments, first by performing data assimilation on single experiments then on sets of experiments.

4.1. Lead's impact on the calculation of ALFRED core's reactivity

Using the formulas that were presented in the methodology section, we quantified the uncertainty coming from the nuclear data in the multiplication factor calculation, for the ALFRED reactor core. We then calculated the uncertainty coming from lead. We also compared it with the uncertainty coming from other isotopes. The results are presented in the table I. The total uncertainty can be found in the

first line, the uncertainty coming from lead and its share in the total variance (s_{pb}) in the middle line. Last lines present the uncertainty coming from plutonium and uranium and their variance share.

Table I. Uncertainty of the multiplication factor calculation.

	Uncertainty	Share of the variance
Total	1227pcm	100%
Pb	98pcm	0.6%
Pu	926pcm	57%
U	783pcm	41%

The main results of this analysis is that lead has little impact on the uncertainty in the calculation of the multiplication factor as it accounts for 0.6% of this variance. The isotopes that have the main impact on the uncertainty are those of the fuel. Here we see that the share of the variance attributable to the neutrons interactions with the plutonium is equal to 57%.

In this context, to reduce uncertainty in the reactivity calculations of lead-cooled fast reactors such as ALFRED, one should focus on experiments that have the same fuel characteristics as the reactor's fuel and with fast neutron spectrum. We hope to find such experiments in the ICSBEP database.

4.2. Nuclear data assimilation on the ICSBEP experiments

After retrieving the sensitivity profile of every fast spectrum ICSBEP experiment, we used them to assess their representativeness with the ALFRED core. This representativeness factor allows to compare the behavior of every experiment with the behavior of the ALFRED core regarding nuclear data. The most representative experiments of the ICSBEP database were then used to do data assimilation and try to reduce the nuclear data uncertainty.

Table II. Data assimilation on experiments.

Name of the experiment	Fuel type	Reflector	$r_{E/A}$	Ω	u_{ND}^*
MIX-COMP-FAST-006	(Pu,U)-oxide	Na, U_{dep} , Steel	0.958	0.998	356pcm
MIX-COMP-FAST-005	(Pu,U)-carbide	U_{dep}	0.951	0.995	391pcm
MIX-COMP-FAST-001	(Pu,U)-oxide	Na, U_{dep}	0.946	0.997	405pcm
MIX-MISC-FAST-002	(Pu,U)-oxide	U_{dep} , Steel	0.880	0.985	584pcm
MIX-MISC-FAST-003	(Pu,U)-oxide	U_{dep} , Steel	0.850	0.981	725pcm
PU-MET-FAST-033	(Pu,U)-metal	Graphite	0.784	0.984	772pcm
MIX-MET-FAST-011	(Pu,U)-metal	Graphite	0.775	0.982	788pcm

Seven experiments of the ICSBEP database have a representativeness of more than 0.75 to the ALFRED core. Those experiments are presented in table II. Their reference name in the ICSBEP database is presented in the first column, a small description of their composition, with the elements of their fuel and reflector, is presented in the following two columns. We then showed their representativeness factor with the ALFRED core, their neutronic weight, which describes their quality, and finally the *a posteriori* uncertainty of the reactivity calculation of the ALFRED core, after having assimilated the nuclear data on each one of the experiments.

Among the other experiments, not shown in table II, two groups can be identified. The first one con-

tains experiments with low level representativeness, as they were built with high enriched uranium when the ALFRED core's fuel is composed of only 0.2% of ^{235}U . The second one contains experiments with a representativeness around 0.65. They are mainly composed of plutonium in a simple geometry. There are 46 experiments in this range of representativeness. The uncertainty reduction obtained when trying to assimilate data on them is average, as they give information mainly on the plutonium cross sections.

We can see in the table that none of the highly representative experiments have a lead reflector or even sensitivities to lead cross sections of the same order of magnitude than the ALFRED core. There are four experiments in the database that meet this criterion, one is composed of plutonium sphere reflected with lead, with a representativeness of 0.66 and the three others are composed of spheres or cylinders of high-enriched uranium surrounded by lead, with a representativeness of less than 0.1. As explained earlier, the fuel has the main impact on representativeness.

4.3. Detailed study of the composition of the ALFRED core

In the previous section, we have searched the entire ICSBEP database to find representative experiments on which we could perform nuclear data assimilation. With this approach, the minimum uncertainty that can be reached is 356 pcm, but we saw that none of the experiments described exactly the ALFRED core. To further reduce uncertainty, we want to assimilate the nuclear data on several experiments at the same time.

In order to do so, we calculated the *a posteriori* uncertainty of every set of experiments composed of one to five experiments and kept the sets of experiments that gave the smallest uncertainty. The results are given in table III. The *a posteriori* uncertainty and the number of isotopes covered by each set of experiments selected is represented. We see that considering several experiments allows to cover more isotopes and gives more information about the ALFRED core, thereby reducing uncertainty to 232 pcm when assimilation is performed on five experiments. The five experiments that minimize the uncertainty after data assimilation are PU-MET-FAST-002-001, MIX-COMP-FAST-006-001, IEU-MET-FAST-015-001, IEU-MET-FAST-010-001 and IEU-MET-FAST-006-001. The first two are bare plutonium ad mixed plutonium and uranium reflected by sodium. The last three are a mix of uranium 235 and 238, with steel and aluminum reflectors.

Table III. Minimum *a posteriori* uncertainty achieved based on the number of experiments considered

Number of experiments	u_{ND}^*	Isotopes covered	Number of combinations
1	356pcm	146	168
2	337pcm	152	14,028
3	291pcm	162	776,216
4	263pcm	163	32,018,910
5	232pcm	175	1,050,220,248

To find the best set of experiments, we assimilated the nuclear data on every set of experiments, keeping the one with the minimal *a posteriori* uncertainty. We showed in table III the number of combinations tested to find the best set of experiments depending on the number of experiments considered. This number increases exponentially so it was not possible to try with bigger sets of experiments.

We therefore studied the number of isotopes covered by each experiment to select more experiments. To do so, we built the coverage factor associated to each selected ICSBEP experiment, which allows to identify the isotopes and reactions that have been studied in the benchmark. Of the 380 couples (isotope, reaction) that make up the ALFRED core, 322 are represented in the ICSBEP database. Some isotopes

with negligible contribution to the uncertainty, such as Y, Sn or Sb are not studied in the database, and some reactions such as fission spectrum have been little studied. This is due to the characteristics of the ICSBEP database, as most of the experiments of the benchmark reach criticality but do not generate power like a real reactor core.

To test the relevance of such a selection, we selected the smaller set of experiments that covers all of the isotopes that have an impact on the reactivity calculation of the ALFRED core which consists of 18 experiments. This set of experiments should provide the most accurate description of the core with minimal correlations. The results are presented on the figure 1. We see in blue the number of isotopes covered that increases with the number of experiments considered and in red the *a posteriori* uncertainty after data assimilation on the subset of the first experiments.

Figure 1. Nuclear data assimilation on a set of experiments covering all isotopes

The best *a posteriori* uncertainty reached with data assimilation on a sub-set of experiments is of 355 pcm, reached with 14 experiments. If the uncertainty reduction can decrease, it is due to the correlation penalty that was imposed to avoid overfitting. This result does not show substantial improvement in terms of *a posteriori* uncertainty, and further studies to find a better criteria for selecting experiments should be conducted.

5. CONCLUSION

In this article, we have studied the discrepancies between the true value and the calculated value of the reactivity attributable to uncertainties in nuclear data for lead-cooled fast neutron reactors. Our case study is a simplified model of the ALFRED core.

We first studied the impact of the presence of lead in the core. We showed that its share of variance is negligible compared to the share of variance of the isotopes of the fuel, meaning that its impact on the uncertainty is low.

We then tried to reduce the uncertainty by performing data assimilation on the experiments of the ICSBEP database. In this benchmark we found some very representative experiments, up to 0.96, that allowed us to reduce significantly the uncertainty, from 1227 pcm to 356 pcm. However, none of the experiments were considered similar enough to the ALFRED core as they do not have the same characteristics of power and composition as the nuclear reactor core. Nevertheless, by considering sets of experiments, it was still possible to improve the data assimilation process. We reached an *a posteriori* uncertainty of 232 pcm, with a set of 5 experiments.

Finally, conventional method of uncertainty reduction works well on Lead-cooled Fast Reactors regarding nuclear data impact on multiplication factor calculation and it is possible to extract a great deal of information from historical experiments, even if they were not designed for the study of this kind of reactors.

This first analysis will be improved in a following work, by trying other definitions of the coverage factor profile that can be more useful, but also by studying the main counter reactions. Indeed, this study can be carried out with other reactivity coefficients like Doppler, fuel expansion and coolant void. During all of the study, we used COMAC as covariance matrix. We also want to quantify the dependence of the study results to this matrix. Finally, the studies of the uncertainty from the model (u_{Mod}) and the uncertainty from the operating and manufacturing data (u_{OMD}) are still to be done.

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